

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-44-IG-10% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	21	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 44
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 9:45:51 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 19:42:06 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.380	10420372	49.77	1299656
2	5.988	10515835	50.23	1150281

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-43-IG-10% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20221029
Vial:	58	Acq. Method Set:	10%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	4 278
Injection Volume:	1.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/29/2022 19:03:06 CST		
Date Processed:	7/2/2023 15:22:36 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.344	421360	97.87	62492
2	6.015	9190	2.13	1199